

TETR ARCHs

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

Deliverable 2.4

Evaluation Methodology & User Testimonials

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Summary

This Deliverable 2.4, titled *Evaluation Methodology and User Testimonials*, provides a synthesised report of participant engagement across the TETRARCHS project. This includes reflections on participant recruitment and engagement, as well as modes of participation, leading to a series of recommendations for future participatory practices. We close by looking in more detail at participant testimonials in relation to the project themes and objectives.

Introduction: Aim of the Deliverable

This deliverable presents a synthesis of participant engagement across the TETRARCHs project, focusing on how individuals and communities were recruited, involved, and mobilised in experimental workflows. As outlined in the original CHANSE project proposal, TETRARCHs aims to transform the reuse of archaeological data by embedding storytelling practices into every stage of the data lifecycle—from capture and mapping to post-excavation analysis and archival dissemination.

Central to this ambition is the active participation of three key user groups: domain specialists (archaeologists), creative practitioners, and memory institutions. These groups were not only consulted but often co-created the design, execution, and evaluation of experiments across multiple work packages. Where possible, community participation was organised, mainly at the archaeological sites. The involvement of the key user groups was intended to:

- Support the development of critically-aware workflows for data reuse
- Contribute to the creation of the world's first controlled vocabulary for cultural heritage storytelling
- Enable scenario-testing of reuse strategies through narrative outputs
- Provide feedback for the assessment of reuse effectiveness
- Inform best practice recommendations for trusted digital repositories

This report documents when, how, and why participants were engaged in the project's experimental activities and reflects on its methodological implications through testimonials. The testimonials were gathered through snowballing an invitation to reflect on the role and impact participants had in the experiments.

1. Synthesis of Participant Involvement throughout TeTRARCHs Experiments: recruitment strategies, engagement formats, and participatory rationales

Central to TETRARCHS' methodology is the active involvement of diverse user groups—archaeologists, creative practitioners, museum professionals, and communities—in experimental workflows that test legacy data integration, digital documentation, and narrative construction. In this section, we synthesise how participants were recruited, engaged, and mobilised across the project's experimental landscape, drawing on documentation from WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP7 deliverables.

Participants were recruited through a combination of institutional networks, community partnerships, and targeted outreach. Concerning the recruitment of archaeologists, these were drawn from archaeological site teams (both academic and commercial archaeologists) and the network of project partners such as MOLA, Lund University, ZRC SAZU, the University of York, Vilnius University and the University of Antwerp. These participants were often involved in fieldwork or archival practices, contributed domain expertise and were involved in annotation activities geared towards storytelling. Heritage organisations such as Sveriges Hembygdsförbund (national heritage organisation in Sweden) and Fondazione Mont'è Prama (local heritage organisation in Italy) facilitated the recruitment of volunteers and community members. These groups were selected for their proximity to archaeological sites and their existing engagement with cultural heritage. Creative practitioners were selected through a TETRARCHs open call residency and were invited to participate in workshops and storytelling experiments. Additionally, creatives were targeted for an online survey in the gap analysis work in WP3. The involvement of staff members from memory institutions (mostly museums) were drawn from the networks of project partners and, in the case of the archaeological sites, were selected because of their prior involvement in engaging audiences.

In addition to these field- and workshop-based forms of participation, TETRARCHs also engaged participants through a structured consultation strand developed within WP7. This strand focused on archaeology-related creative professionals and specialists—such as filmmakers, journalists, educators, crafts reconstructors, and designers—selected according to criteria that emphasised active community membership and recent engagement with archaeological material. Rather than contributing directly to excavation or storytelling production, these participants were involved as reflective users of archaeological data and digital archives, offering insights into motivations, expectations, and barriers to reuse across different professional and creative contexts.

Participant involvement spanned multiple formats, tailored to the goals of each experiment. For example, in the Annotation and Metadata Enrichment Workshops (WP3), participants were invited to enrich legacy datasets—such as photographs, illustrations, and 3D models—with emotive, sensory, and narrative metadata. These workshops were conducted both online and in-person, and included structured annotation tasks (e.g., tagging images with affective descriptors), group discussions on metadata gaps and storytelling potential or use of platforms like Omeka-S and AIR for collaborative input. These activities were designed to test the expressiveness of existing metadata standards and inform the development of the Storytelling Data Model (WP3).

In Sweden, Greece, Italy, and Slovenia, participants engaged in field-based experiments like field documentation and interpretation using digital tools. At Västra Vång and Hästhallen, volunteers and museum staff participated in 3D documentation workflows, including drone-based LiDAR scanning. At Hjortsberga, participants used both analogue and LiDAR-derived maps to identify burial features,

annotate visibility, and reflect on usability. At Toumba Serron in Greece, archaeologists and creative practitioners collaborated on multimedia documentation. At Tharros, Italy, local community members and archaeologists were engaged in on-site data-gathering and storytelling, followed by and mixed-group narrative creation. At Västra Vång, Hästhallen and Toumba Serron, local volunteers, museum staff, creative practitioners and field team members were engaged in community critiques for feedback collection.

Regarding the different storytelling experiments, participants were invited to construct narratives using enriched datasets. Formats included card games, blog posts, and educational resources, community storytelling sessions and collaborative writing and public engagement outputs such as online exhibitions. These experiments foregrounded the role of lived experience, emotion, and imagination in archaeological interpretation, and were designed to test the reuse potential of enriched legacy data. WP7 complemented these engagement formats through a multi-method consultation approach designed to capture how different communities actually encounter and reuse archaeological data. This included semi-structured interviews exploring motivations and data needs, an exploratory workshop bringing archaeologists together with non-professional archaeology communities to refine and validate use cases, and an eye-tracking experiment observing how participants navigated major archaeological data platforms. A post-experiment questionnaire further captured reflections on effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction. Together, these methods extended participation beyond co-creation to include evaluation, reflection, and critical assessment of reuse practices.

2. Cross-Experiment Analysis: Patterns of Participation and Reuse in TETRARCHs

The TETRARCHs project conducted a diverse set of experiments across Europe, engaging domain specialists, creative practitioners, and memory institutions in the co-creation, enrichment, and reuse of archaeological data. While each experiment was tailored to its local context and audience, several cross-cutting themes and methodological insights emerged.

Across all experiments, participant involvement was structured around three primary modes.

Co-documentation: Participants were directly involved in the creation and annotation of archaeological data. This included activities such as 3D scanning at Hästhallen and field documentation at Västra Vång, where volunteers and museum staff contributed to the recording process alongside archaeologists, which happened at Toumba Serron and Tharros as well.

Metadata enrichment: Participants helped enhance legacy datasets by adding expressive, narrative-driven metadata. For example, in the WP2 MOLA photographic reuse workshops and the WP3 enrichment session, users tagged images of legacy data and newly created data and records with terms that, upon analysis, demonstrated a focus on emotional, sensory, and descriptive experience. These terms provide insight in the need to embrace emotional, sensory and personal detail to improve the storytelling potential of archaeological data.

Storytelling and reuse: Participants used enriched archaeological data to craft narratives in various formats. At sites like Tharros (Italy), Toumba Serron (Greece) and Kingston Horsefair (England), community members, artists, and students created stories, artworks, games, and educational resources that reinterpreted archaeological findings for broader audiences.

Findings from WP7 reinforce and contextualise these patterns by demonstrating that reuse is shaped not only by creative engagement, but also by information behaviour and interface design. Interviews and eye-tracking experiments revealed that difficulties in reuse frequently arise not from a lack of interest or understanding, but from the archaeological professional logic embedded in archive structures, metadata hierarchies, and navigation systems. Participants relied heavily on visual cues, first impressions, and familiar search behaviours, often struggling when platforms required specialised disciplinary knowledge. These insights underline the importance of aligning participatory data practices with diverse user logics if reuse is to extend beyond experimental settings.

3. Recommendations for Future Participatory Practices

Based on cross-experiment findings and participant reflections, the following recommendations are proposed to guide future participatory practices in archaeology and heritage data reuse. These strategies aim to foster inclusivity, creativity, and sustainability in collaborative workflows.

Design Modular Workflows for Varied Expertise: Develop flexible participation structures that allow individuals to engage according to their skills, interests, and comfort levels—whether as observers, annotators or storytellers. For example, at the Hjortsberga burial ground experiment, participants were given both analogue and LiDAR-derived maps and invited to annotate whichever format they found most intuitive. Some focused on visual identification, while others contributed keywords or reflections. This modular approach enabled meaningful engagement across a spectrum of archaeological literacy. This was also visible in WP7, where participants engaged in enrichment or storytelling differently, not only because of experiment design, but because each user group had fundamentally different information behaviours, expectations, and thresholds for accuracy.

Include Prompts and Explanatory Metadata Categories: Provide structured prompts, examples, and thematic categories to help participants generate rich, descriptive metadata that goes beyond technical tags. In Tharros, Italy, participants were prompted with questions co-designed by TETRARCHs and the cultural partner – Fondazione Mont’e Prama – and focused around three key themes (sensation, imagination, change), e.g., “You are at Tharros in the past. The sun is setting. What do you imagine?”; “What traces of change, abandonment, or renewal do you notice here?” WP7 shows that non-archaeologists struggle not because data is hard to understand but because archive organisation follows archaeological logic rather than user logic. Explanatory metadata categories can translate archaeological concepts for broader audiences. However, we must also acknowledge the insights from the MOLA photographic reuse workshops, where participants were asked to annotate images with terms that were instinctive to them. This free-form approach naturally led towards emotion, action and atmosphere-focused results.

Mix Participant Groups to Foster Dialogue and Mutual Learning: Intentionally combine specialists, creatives, and community members in shared activities to encourage cross-disciplinary exchange and to challenge assumptions. For example, at Tharros (Italy), mixed groups of archaeologists, artists, and local residents co-created stories using legacy photographs and personal reflections. This led to unexpected insights, such as a fisherman linking his life story to the site’s history, and an archaeologist reconsidering “abandoned interpretations” as valid narrative material. This was also palpable in WP7, where the mixed participant workshop generated richer insights and unintended interpretative connections.

Document the Documentation Process: Capture not just the data, but the context in which it was created—through video, audio, annotations, or reflective journalling. For example, at Västra Vång, 360° video recordings of pre- and post-excavation meetings revealed how archaeologists reused legacy data to shape field strategies. These recordings became part of the interpretative archive, offering insight into decision-making and collaborative reasoning.

Ensure Digital Platforms Are Accessible, Multilingual, and Mobile-Friendly: Design interfaces that accommodate diverse users, including those with limited digital literacy or language barriers. For example, during the Hästhallen 3D documentation experiment, some volunteers struggled with navigating the AIR platform. Feedback highlighted the need for clearer instructions, simplified navigation, and mobile compatibility. In WP7, the eye-tracking results show that users rely heavily on what “catches the eye first” and struggle when interfaces require complex navigation. These findings

emphasise that accessibility is not only a technical concern, but a participatory one, directly shaping who is able to engage with and reuse archaeological data.

Link Stories to Object Records for Narrative Reuse and Traceability: Create mechanisms to associate participant-generated stories, annotations, and reflections with the original data records—ideally within the same archival system. For example, at Blekinge Museum, a story created by museum staff was embedded directly into the AIR report and linked to the relevant 3D models and context records. Participants in the follow-up workshop could trace the narrative back to its source data and add their own keywords and impressions. In contrast, the Omeka-S interface used at Toumba Serron (Greece) and Tharros (Italy) was considered user-friendly, but at the time of experimentation could not link narratives back to the wider archaeological datasets.

4. Testimonial Voices

Testimonial voices were gathered through two channels: an open call for reflections, and reactions during the different experiments and activities. The open call invited collaborators to share their experiences with TETRARCHs, guided by prompts aligned with the project's core values—openness, inclusivity, human-centred design, and ethical data reuse. These submissions included written, audio, and survey-based testimonials from creative practitioners, community members, archaeologists, and data professionals. In parallel, additional reflections were documented within field reports and workshop transcripts, offering contextual insights from participants who engaged in experiments across Italy, Greece, Slovenia, and the UK.

The testimonials (Appendix 1) reveal several recurring themes that align closely with the project's objectives. Participants consistently described their experiences as transformative, imaginative, and emotionally resonant. Whether through storytelling, artistic creation, or field-based reflection, they expressed a deepened connection to archaeological data and its human dimensions. Many testimonials highlight the project's inclusive ethos—its ability to bring together professionals, non-specialists, and creatives in shared spaces of knowledge production. Participants valued being heard, being invited to contribute, and seeing their input reflected in project outputs. Artists and community members emphasised how TETRARCHs challenged conventional notions of archaeological knowledge. Concepts like “vertical time,” improvisation, and non-linear storytelling emerged as powerful metaphors for rethinking data reuse and interpretation. Practitioners noted the project's relevance to broader debates in heritage data management, including transparency, paradata, and GDPR. The project's consultations and exhibitions were seen as timely interventions in evolving professional standards.

These testimonials are not merely affirmations of success—they are textured, situated responses that reveal both the strengths and the tensions of TETRARCHs' participatory model. Although the focus on a human-centred design is praised, the contrast between these experimental (academic research) spaces and the realities of commercial fieldwork or archival practice—where data is often treated as objective and decontextualised—highlights the challenge of embedding such approaches more broadly.

The emotional resonance of the project is striking. Participants spoke of imagination, memory, and personal transformation. However, this emotional depth also demands care. Projects that evoke strong personal responses must be prepared to support participants beyond the moment of engagement. While TETRARCHs created safe and inclusive environments, future work should consider how to embed long-term care practices and ethical follow-up.

The project succeeded in flattening hierarchies and fostering mutual respect. Participants valued being treated as equals and co-creators. Yet, some reflections hint at asymmetries in expectations and benefits. For example, artists and community members emphasised the importance of personal relevance and reciprocity—reminding us that participatory work must be mutually beneficial and not extractive.

Moreover, while creative practitioners were empowered to reinterpret data, archaeologists occasionally expressed discomfort at the reframing of their work. This tension—between disciplinary rigor and creative openness—is productive, but must be navigated with care and transparency.

The testimonial from the data manager also raises a critical issue: how to balance transparency and credit with the right to anonymity in digital field records. This is especially relevant in commercial archaeology, where data workflows are complex and often opaque. TETRARCHs' consultations

surfaced these tensions, but solutions remain provisional. Future work should explore how expressive metadata and storytelling can coexist with ethical data governance.

These testimonials are organised based on the core message and pseudo-anonymised to comply with the consent that was given.

Appendix 1. Participant Testimonials

Testimonials referring to community engagement and empowerment

“The fact that we involve the local community in particular is very important because they must be the first to truly know the history of their territory... this will make us even more aware, respectful, and proud.”

— Heritage professional, Italy

“These events are very pleasant and fun... you learn a lot and above all there is sharing.”

— Community participant from Italy

“I’m curious and happy to discover my country with different eyes.”

— Community participant, Italy

Testimonials referring to creative and reflective practice

“Everything was born in those 10 minutes without a cell phone thinking, where we were, what we were, who we are and where we want to go.”

— Community participant, Italy

“My imagination and creativity were greatly stimulated... the creation of the stories took me to a new dimension and brought me closer to archaeology.”

— Community participant, Italy

“Perhaps abandoned interpretations... might still be valuable for storytelling, as ‘fodder’ for alternate, functional histories.”

— Professional archaeologist, the excavation team, Italy

Testimonials referring to cross-disciplinary inspiration

“TETRARCHs has been an eye-opener to the world of archaeology... it gave me an intimate encounter with what goes on behind the scenes.”

— Creative resident

“It was inspiring to work with archaeologists and feel the passion they have... it helped me connect more deeply with the past and my own humanity.”

— Creative resident

Testimonials referring to ethical and sectoral reflection

“My experience of working with TETRARCHs has been that of inclusivity, open-mindedness, and the willingness to pursue a ‘human-centred’ approach... The final exhibition explored these ideas in a way I found both exciting and challenging.”

— Data Manager, UK

“The leaders of the project created a safe and productive space... I felt included and got feedback that my input was taken into account even months after the training ended.”

— Archaeologist, Slovenia

TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.

For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.

For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.

Get in touch:

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